

CYSTIN AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT. ESTIMATION OF COPPER, CADMIUM, COBALT, NICKEL, AND ZINC ; AND THEIR SEPARATION FROM CALCIUM, BARIUM AND MAGNESIUM

BY PRIVADARANJAN RAY AND AJITSANKAR BHADURI

Cystin has been used as an analytical reagent with satisfactory results for the estimation of copper, cadmium, cobalt, nickel and zinc, as well as for the separation of the latter three elements from calcium, barium and magnesium. Attempt to separate zinc from iron and aluminium in the presence of tartaric or sulphosalicylic acid in ammoniacal solution led, however, to no fruitful results. The precipitation of zinc under these circumstances was considerably retarded, or even more or less completely inhibited, depending upon the amount of iron or of sulphosalicylic acid present, though tartaric acid or sulphosalicylic acid alone has got no effect.

Cystin is known to form a bright blue, silky, crystalline copper compound, resembling copper glycine. This is insoluble in water and belongs obviously to the class of inner metallic complex salts like the latter. Its structure can, therefore, be represented by the planar square configuration as given below :

Copper cystin.

Cystin.

An insoluble cadmium compound of cystin has also been described. It was therefore considered desirable to explore the possibility of its usefulness as an analytical reagent. Cystin has now been found to react also with cobalt, nickel and zinc salts under suitable conditions to form insoluble compounds, and methods have been developed for the estimation of all these elements, as well as of copper and cadmium, in the form of their cystin salts. The reagent has also been found to give useful results in the separation of cobalt, nickel and zinc from the alkaline earths and magnesium. On the other hand, though iron or aluminium does not react with cystin, it has not been found possible to separate zinc from them even in the presence of masking reagents like tartaric acid or sulphosalicylic acid, which are known to form soluble complexes with these elements.

Cystin is sparingly soluble in water and in all common organic solvents, but dissolves in dilute mineral acids and ammonia. The reagent was therefore used in dilute HCl solution. Strong acids, however, decompose cystin with liberation of H₂S. An 1% solution of cystin in normal (1-N) hydrochloric acid was employed in the present work.

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimation of Copper

For the preparation of copper cystin a solution of cystin in dilute hydrochloric acid was added in slight excess to an acidified solution of copper sulphate. The mixture was heated to boiling and treated with dilute ammonia till it smelt of the latter. The bright blue, silky precipitate was allowed to settle on the water-bath, filtered and washed with hot slightly ammoniacal water till free from cystin. The precipitate was then washed with absolute alcohol and finally with anhydrous ether. The product was afterwards kept in a sulphuric acid desiccator for about half an hour. The substance is soluble in excess of ammonia and also in dilute acids.

Copper was estimated volumetrically after decomposition of the substance with fuming nitric acid. [Found : Cu, 19.86, 19.95. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires $\frac{2}{5}$ Cu, 19.89 per cent].

Procedure.—The solution, containing about 0.1 g. of copper, was diluted to 250 c.c. and heated to boiling. To the hot solution about 40 c.c. of the reagent (1% cystin in *N*-HCl) were added. The mixture was then treated with ammonia, drop by drop, till it became distinctly alkaline, when the copper cystin separated completely in the form of a bright blue, silky crystalline precipitate. This was allowed to stand on the water-bath and then filtered in a tared asbestos-based Gooch crucible. The precipitate was washed with hot ammoniacal water until free from cystin. Usually 5 to 6 washings were enough. It was then washed three times with absolute alcohol and finally thrice with anhydrous ether on the pump. The crucible with the precipitate was afterwards kept in a sulphuric acid desiccator for half an hour and then immediately weighed. The weight of copper was calculated from the formula given above. Cu = 19.89%. The results are collected in Table I.

TABLE I

Cu present.	Cu-cystin.	Cu found.	Cu present.	Cu-cystin.	Cu found.
0.03258 g.	0.1639 g.	0.03260 g.	0.04402 g.	0.2201 g.	0.04377 g.
0.02671	0.1339	0.02664	0.05509	0.2760	0.05489
0.01460	0.0729	0.01450	0.00881	0.0446	0.00887
0.02086	0.1047	0.02083	0.0207	0.0104	0.00207
0.03111	0.1564	0.03111	0.00103	0.0052	0.00203

Estimation of Cadmium

Cadmium cystin was precipitated in the same way as the copper compound. This was washed with hot ammoniacal water till free from cystin and then with hot distilled water. The fine white, silky precipitate was afterwards dried at a temperature of 150° to a constant weight. [Found : Cd, 32.10, 32.06. $\text{Cd}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4)$ requires Cd, 32.07 per cent].

Procedure.—The silky white precipitate of cadmium cystin, obtained as described above, was filtered on a tared asbestos Gooch, washed with hot water containing a little ammonia (1%) until free from cystin, and dried to a constant weight at 105°. Cd = 32.07%. Table II gives the results obtained.

TABLE II

Cd present.	Cd-cystin.	Cd found.	Cd present.	Cd-cystin.	Cd found.
0.09038 g.	0.2839 g.	0.09103 g.	0.03882 g.	0.1210 g.	0.03880 g.
0.07764	0.2423	0.07770	0.01354	0.0423	0.01356
0.06470	0.2016	0.06464	0.01971	0.0613	0.01966
0.05176	0.1616	0.05181	0.00986	0.0307	0.00984
0.05307	0.1655	0.05305	0.00657	0.0205	0.00657

Estimation of Cobalt

Cobalt cystin was prepared in the same way as the corresponding copper or cadmium compound. An excess of cystin was used in order to prevent any precipitation of cobalt hydroxide by ammonia. An excess of ammonia should be avoided. The light pink coloured precipitate was allowed to settle by keeping it on the water-bath. This was filtered, washed at first by decantation with hot 1% ammonia solution till free from cystin and then with hot water. The precipitate was finally washed with absolute alcohol, followed by anhydrous ether, and then left for about 30 minutes in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 before being weighed. [Found: Co, 18.72. $Co(C_4H_{10}N_2S_2O_4) \cdot H_2O$ requires Co, 18.71 per cent].

Table III gives the results obtained.

TABLE III

Co present.	Co-cystin.	Co found.	Co present.	Co-cystin.	Co found.
0.02486 g.	0.1331 g.	0.02490 g.	0.01591 g.	0.0851 g.	0.01592 g.
0.02188	0.1172	0.02188	0.01492	0.0798	0.01495
0.02088	0.1116	0.02085	0.00249	0.0133	0.00249
0.01989	0.1064	0.01990	0.00995	0.0532	0.00996
0.01790	0.0957	0.01790	0.00119	0.0063	0.00118
0.01642	0.0878	0.01643	0.00099	0.0053	0.00099

Cobalt can be easily separated from Ca, Ba or Mg by this method. Ammonia employed for precipitation should, however, be freshly prepared to avoid the formation of carbonate. Some of the results obtained are given in Table IV.

In the presence of magnesium, cobalt was precipitated by cystin after the addition of some ammonium chloride to prevent the precipitation of magnesium hydroxide. The precipitate of cobalt cystin was dissolved in a little dilute hydrochloric acid and

the cobalt was reprecipitated from the solution by cystin following the usual procedure. Nevertheless, the results indicate a slight absorption of magnesium by the cobalt precipitate. In the filtrate from cobalt cystin calcium was estimated volumetrically after precipitation as oxalate. Barium was estimated gravimetrically as BaSO_4 , and magnesium as $\text{Mg}_2\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$.

TABLE IV

Metal present.	Cobalt cystin.	Metal found.	Metal present.	Cobalt cystin.	Metal found.
Co, 0.00995 g Ca, 0.02164	0.0532 g.	0.00996 g.	Co, 0.01989 g. Ba, 0.01310	0.1065 g.	0.01992 g. 0.01310
Co, 0.00995 Ca, 0.03246	0.0534	0.00999 0.03234	Co, 0.00995 Mg, 0.01665	0.0536	0.01003 0.01650
Co, 0.01939 Ca, 0.01082	0.1063	0.01988	Co, 0.00995 Mg, 0.04995	0.0539	0.01009 0.04962
Co, 0.00995 Ba, 0.03930	0.0533	0.00998	Co, 0.01989 Mg, 0.01665	0.1063	0.01988
Co, 0.00995 Ba, 0.01310	0.0534	0.01000	Co, 0.01989 Mg, 0.06660	0.1077	0.02014
Co, 0.00995 Ba, 0.02620	0.0534	0.01000	Ca, 0.02984 Mg, 0.08325	0.1619	0.03019

Estimation of Nickel

Nickel was estimated by following the procedure prescribed for cadmium. The light green precipitate of nickel cystin was dried at 105° . [Found: Ni, 18.68. $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 18.65 per cent].

The results are given in Table V.

TABLE V

Nickel present.	Ni-cystin.	Ni found.	Nickel present.	Ni-cystin.	Ni found.
0.03786 g.	0.2025 g.	0.03780 g.	0.01578 g.	0.0848 g.	0.01582 g.
0.02525	0.1356	0.02527	0.01052	0.0564	0.01053
0.12610	0.1399	0.02610	0.00210	0.0113	0.00210
0.02104	0.1127	0.02102	0.00105	0.0056	0.00105

Nickel was separated from calcium, barium and magnesium by precipitation with cystin using freshly prepared carbonate-free ammonia. The results are collected in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Metal present.	Nickel cystin.	Metal found.	Metal present.	Nickel cystin.	Metal found.
Ni, 0.01052 g. Ca, 0.01082	0.0562 g.	0.01048 g.	Ni, 0.02104 g. Ba, 0.01310	0.1143 g.	0.02132 g. 0.01307
Ni, 0.01052 Ca, 0.02164	0.0567	0.01058	Ni, 0.02104 Ba, 0.02620	0.1131	0.02109
Ni, 0.01052 Ca, 0.03246	0.0565	0.01053	Ni, 0.02104 Ba, 0.03930	0.1129	0.02106
Ni, 0.02104 Ca, 0.02164	0.1121	0.02091	Ni, 0.01052 Mg, 0.03330	0.0567	0.01052
Ni, 0.02104 Ca, 0.01082	0.1144	0.02134 0.01094	Ni, 0.01052 Mg, 0.04995	0.0563	0.01050
Ni, 0.01052 Ba, 0.02120	0.0564	0.01053 0.02616	Ni, 0.01052 Mg, 0.01665	0.0562	0.01049 0.01676
Ni, 0.01052 Ba, 0.03930	0.0563	0.01051	Ni, 0.02104 Mg, 0.03330	0.1128	0.02104
			Ni, 0.03156 Mg, 0.04995	0.1698	0.03150

Calcium, barium and magnesium were estimated as stated before.

Estimation of Zinc

Zinc cystin was obtained as a milky white precipitate following the procedure described under cadmium. The precipitate was dried at 105°-110°. The precipitate is fairly soluble in ammonia in presence of ammonium salts. [Found: Zn, 21.56. Zn (C₂H₁₀N₂S₂O₄) requires Zn, 21.55 per cent]. Table VII shows the results obtained.

TABLE VII

Zn present.	Zn-cystin.	Zn found.	Zn present.	Zn-cystin.	Zn found.
0.03351 g.	0.1560 g.	0.03359 g.	0.01675 g.	0.0777 g.	0.01674 g.
0.02345	0.1089	0.02346	0.01117	0.0519	0.01118
0.02234	0.1035	0.02230	0.00559	0.0258	0.00555
0.02011	0.0932	0.02009	0.00223	0.0102	0.00221

Zinc was separated from calcium, barium and magnesium by precipitation with cystin. The excess acid in the solution in all these cases was first neutralised with sodium bicarbonate prior to the addition of ammonia. Results are given in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Metal present.	Zn-cystin.	Metal found.	Metal present.	Zn-cystin.	Metal found.
Zn, 0.01061 g. Ca, 0.01082	0.0491 g.	0.01059 g.	Zn, 0.01061 g. Ba, 0.01310	0.0484 g.	0.01050 g.
Zn, 0.01061 Ca, 0.02164	0.0492	0.01060 0.02164	Zn, 0.01061 Ba, 0.03930	0.0491	0.01059
Zn, 0.01061 Ca, 0.03246	0.0492	0.01068	Zn, 0.02122 Ba, 0.01310	0.0983	0.02120
Zn, 0.02122 Ca, 0.01082	0.0982	0.02116	Zn, 0.02122 Ba, 0.02620	0.0983	0.02120
Zn, 0.02122 Cr, 0.02164	0.0982	0.02116	Zn, 0.02122 Ba, 0.0393	0.0983	0.02118
Zn, 0.02122 Ca, 0.03246	0.0985	0.02122 0.03232	Zn, 0.01061 Mg, 0.04995	0.0492	0.01060
Zn, 0.01061 Ba, 0.02620	0.0492	0.01060 0.02607	Zn, 0.02122 Mg, 0.01665	0.0985	0.02122 0.02674
			Zn, 0.02122 Mg, 3.03330 or 0.04995	0.0983	0.02119

Calcium, barium and magnesium were estimated as in the previous cases.

An attempt to separate zinc from iron in presence of alkaline tartrates led to no fruitful results. It was found that though tartaric acid even in large excess had no effect on the precipitation of zinc by cystin, presence of iron, however, considerably retarded its precipitation. With a large excess of iron no precipitation of zinc occurred at all. This is apparent from the results collected in Table IX below.

TABLE IX

Zinc present = 0.01117 g.

Fe added.	Rochelle salt added.	Zn-cystin.	Zn found.
—	2 g.	0.05185 g.	0.01117 g.
—	5	0.05287	0.01118
—	10	0.05180	0.01116
—	20	0.05178	0.01116
0.00433 g.	5	0.05115	0.01105
0.00816	"	0.04517	0.00973
0.01298	"	0.03976	0.00857
0.02597	"	0.02216	0.00478
0.04328	"	No precipitation	

Similar results were obtained in an attempt to separate zinc as zinc cystin from iron and aluminium in presence of sulphosalicylic acid which is known to form complexes with the latter metals. But as these complexes break up at the boiling temperature, the precipitation of zinc was carried out in all these cases by heating the mixture on the water-bath only, to prevent any possible separation of the hydroxides of iron and aluminium. Table X gives some results of such estimations. Like tartaric acid, sulphosalicylic acid itself has got no effect on the precipitation of zinc by cystin in alkaline medium. The solution in all these cases was neutralised with NaHCO_3 before the addition of ammonia for precipitating zinc. This was to prevent the formation of much ammonium salts which tended to keep the zinc cystin in solution.

TABLE X

Zinc present = 0.01064 g.

Fe or Al.	Sulphosalicylic acid.	Reagent.	Zn-cystin.	Zn found.
—	2.5 g.	Slight excess	0.04944 g.	0.01065 g.
—	4.0	„	0.04952	0.01067
—	5.0	„	0.04960	0.01069
Fe, 0.04435 g.	5.0	0.10 g.	0.03692	0.00706
„	4.0	„	0.04422	0.00953
„	3.0	„	0.04597	0.00987
„	2.0	„	Fe(OH) ₃ co-precipitated.	
„	2.5	0.20	0.04917	0.01060
„	„	0.18	0.04926	0.01062
„	„	0.15	0.04795	0.01034
0.0887	5.0	0.20	0.03687	0.00795
„	„	0.30	0.04170	0.00898
„	„	0.40	0.04760	0.01026
„	„	0.45	0.04918	0.01060
Al, 0.02490	1.0	0.10	0.04424	0.00953
„	„	0.12	0.04574	0.00986
„	„	0.15	0.04759	0.01026
„	„	0.18	0.04952	0.01067
0.0497	2.0	0.20	0.04504	0.00970
„	„	0.25	0.04964	0.01070

In the case of aluminium, the precipitate first formed, was, after the decantation of the supernatant liquid, dissolved in a little dilute hydrochloric acid and then re-precipitated by adding a little more cystin and sulphosalicylic acid.

An examination of Table X reveals certain interesting points. In the presence of a definite quantity of iron an increase of sulphosalicylic acid increasingly retards the precipitation of zinc; this can, however, be counteracted by increasing the amount of the reagent added. In fact, satisfactory results have been obtained, in the presence of both iron and aluminium, by adding a fairly large excess of the reagent. This seems to suggest that cystin reacts in some way or other with the sulphosalicylic acid complex of iron and aluminium, and thus rendering itself more or less unavailable for the precipitation of zinc. A similar explanation also applies to the case of iron tartrate complex.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received February 13, 1950